

Evolution of Yolo Architectures: Trends, Applications and Future Research Directions for Object Detection

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Abstract—Object detection plays an important role in modern computer vision, supporting applications such as autonomous driving, security monitoring, medical imaging, and industrial automation. Among the different deep learning methods, the You Only Look Once (YOLO) family has gained exceptional attention for its real-time detection capability and high accuracy. From its first release YOLO has evolved through several versions—each improving the architecture, detection performance, and processing speed. This paper surveys the development and real-world applicability of the YOLO family of single-stage object detectors. The evolution from YOLOv1 through YOLOv11 is summarized. It emphasizes milestones such as anchor boxes and multi-scale prediction (v2–v3). It also highlights engineering and augmentation strategies (v4–v5). Reparameterization and deployment-centric optimizations is introduced in v6–v7. Anchor-free designs and user-focused tooling appears in v8 and recent advances integrating gradient optimization, attention, and transformer modules appear in v9–v11. For each generation it is highlighted trade-offs among accuracy, inference speed, and resource demands. This paper also surveys prominent application domains—autonomous driving, surveillance, health-care imaging, retail automation, agriculture, robotics, and environmental monitoring—illustrating YOLO’s suitability for latency-sensitive tasks. Finally, it discusses existing challenges and potential research directions to make YOLO-based systems more efficient and adaptable to real-world scenarios.

Index Terms—YOLO, object detection, deep learning, real-time detection, computer vision, YOLO versions

I. INTRODUCTION

Understanding of an image is based on what objects it consists of, where the objects are placed and how the objects appear to be. The human perception of understanding images is by transmuting the light entering through the eyes into brain signals. The human brain already has preconceived images in its memory, which helps in comparing and identifying these signals, by assessing the shapes and patterns of the image in the visual cortex and mapping them with the memory and

context, the outcome is produced, i.e. identification of the objects in the image is done in just a blink of an eye. With the breakthrough in the tech industry over the last decade, the progress of object detection has accelerated significantly. Object detection has grown to become one of the most major and powerful technologies in the present world. It is a primary part of Computer Vision (CV) [1]. Computer vision seeks to mirror and widen the proficiencies of human perception through computational methods. It permits the system to decipher the components of visual inputs – such as motion detection, face recognition, object identification, and more. The domain has evolved substantially with the need of deep learning algorithms, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and real time object recognition models like YOLO and Faster R-CNN. The precision and stability of computer vision systems have tremendously elevated due to these developments.

You Only Look Once, famously known as YOLO is a real time object detection algorithm [2]. It redefined how object detection in images and videos are quick and accurate. Before YOLO, object detection is digitally expensive yet very slow. R – CNN (Region - based CNN) being a conventional approach is precise but very slow. It is a time-consuming process – it rendered potential regions first (called region proposals), then a classifier is run on each of these regions separately, finally the results are refined using multiple post-processing steps. This is very inconvenient for real-time applications such as security cameras, self-driving cars, or robotics – where a system must “see” and “affirm” instantly. Hence, Yolo came into the frame making detections rapid, unified, and real-time. Object detection is treated as a single regression problem by YOLO unlike the traditional approaches. Everything in an image is predicted in one go, from a single neural network. Thus, satisfying its name “You Only Look Once” [2].

When an image is input in YOLO, at the beginning, image division takes place – it split the image into $S \times S$ grid, making each grid in charge of detecting the objects whose centers lie within the grid. Following which, bounding box prediction takes place – for each box, x , y coordinates of the cell's center, width and height of the box and the confidence score is predicted by each grid cell. The confidence score is the certainty that an object is contained in a predicted box. Subsequent to this class prediction occurs – class probabilities of each grid cell are predicted based on the existing object in the box. Finally, all the predictions are merged into a single output tensor, that states which objects are present, where they are located at and how confident the model is, to give us a final output. The Figure-1,2,3 shows the above.

Fig. 1: Input image in YOLO

Fig. 2: Image divided into $S \times S$ grid

Fig. 3: Objects detected/ Output tensor

II. CLASSIFICATION OF OBJECT DETECTION FRAMEWORKS

Object detection can be categorized into various types based on the approach used and the output it yields. The two major types of object detection can be classified as Two-Stage object detection and Single-Stage object detection [3].

Two-Stage object detection approach follows a step-by-step method to recognize and group objects in an image. Generation of region proposals (sections of the image that probably comprise of an object) is done in the first stage. These proposals are mere guesses about

the location of the objects, and are not precisely classified. After the identification, each proposed region is classified into particular object categories streamlines the bounding box about the object to make it more specific – the second stage [4]. It tends to be very definite since the model provides extra time to emphasize on certain parts of the image, but it is a digitally slower approach since it uses two different stages to detect and analyze the images. These are broadly used in circumstances where precision is much more important than the speed. The Figure-4 shows the architectural design of two stage

object detection.

Fig. 4: Two-Stage Object Detection

Single Stage object detection the region proposal step completely. Rather than analyzing the image in two different stages, it executes the localization of the object and classification concurrently [5]. This implies that the model looks at the whole image, then estimates and classifies the locations and categories of the object all at once respectively. Due to this optimized method, single stage detectors are much swifter and works better for real time applications such as security surveillance, self-driving cars [6]. These might not be as accurate as the two-stage detectors but are more powerful and are competitive. These are models are suited for speed and efficiency, make them optimal for quick decision making is more integral than perfect accuracy . One of the notable examples is YOLO (You Only Look Once).The Figure-5 shows the architectural design of single stage object detection.

Fig. 5: Single Stage Object Detection

The following outputs can be obtained by the model after just one look:

- (i) The bounding boxes for all the objects detected in the image.

- (ii) Each object classified (labelled).
- (iii) Confidence scores of each prediction.

Object detection is not only improved but entirely redefined by YOLO.

- (i) Object detection is made practical for real-time systems.
- (ii) Pipeline is simplified, removing complex region proposal steps.
- (iii) Foundation for advanced, lightweight, efficient and edge friendly AI is laid.

In today's world, the most extensively used object detection algorithm used in open-source and industry grade applications is YOLO, making it revolutionary.

III. ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN

The algorithm used by YOLO has adopted an exclusive and groundbreaking approach, hence revolutionizing object detection. YOLO performs bounding box regression and object category prediction synchronously in one go through the network by uninterruptedly using the entire image as input, divergent from the Faster R-CNN networks, which implement field-based predictions [2]. Object localization and categorization is combined in an integrated model in this architectural design, notably amplifying the efficiency and detection speed. There are three main components of the YOLO's design, the input layer – feature extraction layer – output layer. It is designed for localization of objects precisely and classification of categories and position identification.

A. Grid Based Division And Bounding Box Prediction

In YOLO the input image is divided into a grid of evenly scaled cells. Unlike the traditional approaches, using the sliding window method as in R-CNN, the cell-based approach used in YOLO permits the detection of numerous objects in just a single frame [8]. A critical advancement in YOLO is that the grid cell is accountable for estimating an object, provided that the center of the object's bounding box lies in it. This helps in the eradication of overlapping executions and guarantees smooth management. Each input image is divided into $S \times S$ grid size by YOLO, where each grid cell is responsible for objects detection if the center of the object falls within it. A bounding box 'B' is predicted by each grid cell. Each predicted bounding box has five attributes, namely the center coordinates (x, y) , width (w) , height (h) , and the probability, which corresponds to the likelihood that an object lies within the box. Furthermore, N class probabilities are predicted by the grid cell, corresponding to the possible object categories. Overall, each cell of the grid outputs $B \times 5 + N$ values [2].

The total number of estimated values for the entire grid is $S \times S \times (B \times 5 + N)$. These estimated predictions

Fig. 6: The overlap between the ground truth bounding box an object in an image and the predicted bounding box (or region)

form the output tensor, configured as $S \times S \times (B \times 5 + N)$. The confidence score is calculated using the given formula for each bounding box:

$$C = P(\text{obj}) \times \text{IoU}_{\text{truth,pred}} \quad (1)$$

Where, $P(\text{obj})$ stands for the probability that an object is contained in a grid cell, which is 1 if the grid cell contains an object and 0 if it does not, and $\text{IoU}_{\text{truth,pred}}$ denotes the intersection over union (IoU) of the predicted bounding box relative to the ground truth bounding box [2].

B. Handling Overlapping Detections And Non-Maximum Suppression

One of the major challenges faced in object detection, including YOLO is overlapping of bounding boxes formed during detection [2]. It is common for multiple bounding boxes to predict the same object more than once, especially for large objects or such objects that are situated very close to the boundary of numerous grid cells. Without any additional optimization, the results will show multiple overlapping detections for one single object leading to low accuracy and low clarity of the final predictions. To overcome this obstacle, a very important post processing step is implemented by YOLO, known as the Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS), ensuring that the most relevant bounding boxes are registered while eradicating the duplicates. This is done on the basis of the confidence threshold; it is set to shut out the bounding boxes with low confidence substantially decreasing the total number of candidate boxes [9]. When an image is processed, a fixed number of bounding boxes are prophesied by each grid cell and a confidence score is computed for each box. The confidence score illustrates the product of two factors, namely the probability of a box containing an object, and the Intersection over Union (IoU) between the predicted box and the ground truth box. Any box whose confidence score is below a

certain value (confidence threshold), is discarded. Non-Maximum Suppression functions by focusing only on the most confident bounding boxes while suppressing others that considerably overlap with them. The operation is initiated by arranging all persisting bounding boxes in descending order of their confidence scores [2].

Firstly, the box having the highest confidence score is chosen as the “reference box”. Then, for the remaining boxes of the same class, the IoU between these boxes and the “reference box” is calculated by YOLO [10]. The IoU is the proportion of how much overlapping is done by two bounding boxes and can be mathematically defined as:

$$\text{IoU} = \frac{\text{Area of Overlap}}{\text{Area of Union}} \quad (2)$$

If the IoU between the bounding box as well as the selected reference box is higher than the predefined threshold, it indicates the prediction of the same object by the bounding box. Given this circumstance, such bounding boxes are eliminated by YOLO to prevent duplicate detections. If the IoU is lower than the threshold, the box is retained considering it pertains to a separate object. This operation is performed iteratively until there are no overlapping bounding boxes to be checked. This operation ensures minimal duplication and highest accuracy, where each object is depicted by a singular bounding box with the highest confidence. In previous versions of YOLO, a hard NMS technique is in use, where overlapping bounding boxes exceeding the predefined IoU threshold are directly discarded. Nonetheless, later versions of YOLO augmented upgradations for accurate detection. For instance, YOLOv4 incorporated Soft NMS, which does not entirely eliminate overlapping boxes, rather it decreases their confidence scores relatively to the degree of overlap. In complicated images where objects are tightly clustered, this approach is highly effective, since it prevents the risk of eradicating valid detections. Newer implementations such as YOLOv5 and beyond, use Weighted-NMS, in which weighted averages, based on confidence scores, of overlapping boxes are used to merge them together into a single box. This results in more accurate and stable detections, profoundly when there is a slight misalignment in the bounding boxes [10].

To understand the effect of NMS, the following example can be considered. In an image, YOLO detects three bounding boxes around a single flower [10]. If the confidence score of Box A is 0.95, that of Box B is 0.90 and that of Box C is 0.72, Box A is selected as the primary detection or the “reference box”. Then, the IoU of Box B and Box C is compared; if the IoU is high, suppose it is 0.76, Box A is eliminated since it predicts the same object. Then, if the Box C has a lower IoU, suppose it is 0.32. It is obtained as a credible detection, likely indicating a different nearby

object. YOLO ensures precise localization of distinct objects and minimal redundancy in detections using this approach.

Fig. 7: Implementation of Non-Maximum Suppression

The incorporation of Non-Maximum Suppression in YOLO is crucial for enhancing detection accuracy. It also help in reducing untrue positives, which is shown in Figure-7. There would be several overlapping bounding boxes in the final estimation set, without NMS, which would make the model prone to failure in practical settings. By methodically using NMS, YOLO accomplishes an equilibrium between precision and efficiency, facilitating it to carry out real-time object detection without jeopardizing the quality of detection [10].

C. Development of Yolo Versions

With the introduction of Yolo in 2015, it has undergone rapid development since then. The various versions of are described below from start to end [2].

D. YOLOv1(2015) (The foundation of unified detection)

The proposal of YOLOv1 in 2015, by Joseph Redmon and team, marking a breakthrough in computer vision by redefining object detection [2]. Prior to the introduction of YOLO, detectors such as R-CNN, Fast R-CNN, and Faster R-CNN banked on a double step framework, first, the region proposals are generated and then they are classified in the next step. Though these methods are very accurate, they are computationally heavy and incompetent for real-time applications [11]. YOLOv1 put forward a prominent new approach, treating detections as a single regression problem classifying bounding boxes and class probabilities in a single analysis of convolutional neural network (CNN). Considerations taken into account while developing the network architecture of YOLOv1 are simplicity and speed.

An input image of size 448×448 is accepted and then segregated into a 7×7 grid. The liability of each grid cell is to predict two bounding boxes and one class probability distribution for objects having their centers

inside that particular cell. An output vector of size $7 \times 7 \times 30 = 1470$ (for PASCAL VOC dataset having 20 classes, 2 boxes per cell) is produced by each image. The framework included 24 convolutional layers for feature extraction, following which two fully connected layers are implemented to regress bounding box coordinates, class probabilities and object confidence. The region proposal step is eliminated by this grid based, single-shot design, making the system end-to-end trainable [2].

YOLOv1 had a vital element – the loss function, which combined multiple objectives. The measurement of localization error for the predicted box coordinates, with higher weights given to coordinate accuracy. The distinction between the object containing cells and no object containing cells is encouraged by confidence loss with a decreased penalty for cells detecting no objects. Then, mean squared error is used by classification loss, between the predicted and true class probabilities [2]. Hence, localisation precision is balanced by these two components together giving correct class predictions all while addressing the imbalance caused by several empty grid cells. The Image-8 shows the architectural design of the YOLOv1.

Taking the performance into account which is shown in Table-I, YOLOv1 attained a mean Average Precision (mAP) of 63.4% on PASCAL VOC 2007 [12], making it narrowly below the then latest detectors like Fast R-CNN. Nevertheless, the speed of YOLOv1 is unbeaten, standard YOLO ran at 45 frames per second (FPS) and a Fast-YOLO variant reached an astounding speed of 155 FPS and Map of 52.7%. This made YOLOv1 have a breakthrough in the field of real-time operations on standard hardware.

TABLE I: Performance of YOLO models

Model	Dataset	mAP	FPS
YOLO V1	PASCAL VOC 2007	63.40%	45
Fast YOLO V1	PASCAL VOC 2007	52.70%	155

In spite of all the great achievements of YOLOv1, there are notable limitations in this version. Since each grid cell predicted only two boxes and one class, it struggled to detect small objects when multiple objects are close together. There are errors with localization as well due to imprecise and poorly aligned bounding boxes [2]. However, the advantages surpassed over the flaws making it a fundamental contribution.

Advantages:

- (i) High-speed detection for real-time objects
- (ii) Single network (unified) detection

Limitations:

- (i) Overlapping detections and small objects are a hurdle
- (ii) Coarse grid division results in localization errors

Fig. 8: Architecture of YOLOv1

E. YOLOv2/YOLO9000 (Faster, better and broader)

YOLOv2, also known as YOLO9000 is introduced in 2016-2017 as the improvised version of YOLOv1 [13]. Enhancing both accuracy and scalability with preservation of real time performance is the main target. The central framework is upgraded to Darknet-19, a lightweight CNN having 19 convolutional layers and 5 max pooling layers improving the efficiency of feature extraction. The Image-9 shows the architectural design of the YOLOv2.

One of the major advancements in YOLOv2 is the usage of anchor boxes, adapted from Faster R-CNN, which made handling of objects of varying shapes and sizes. The model estimated offsets proportional to pre-defined anchors instead of directly predicting bounding box coordinates, the pre-defined anchors are selected on the concept of k-means clustering on ground truth boxes making them specific for each dataset and more effective [27]. Batch normalization is also implemented in YOLOv2 stabilizing training and decreasing the need for dropout. One more milestone reached by this model is multi-scale training. At the time of training, images of different resolutions between 320x320 and 608x608 are presented arbitrarily. Multiple input sizes could be adapted by the same model, at inference, balancing speed and accuracy based on hardware components [13].

YOLOv2 attained 78.6% mAP on PASCAL VOC 2007 [12] and 21.6% mAP on COCO test-dev [14], surpassing the performance of YOLOv1 whilst continuing to run in real-time (40-90 FPS on input size) which is shown in Table-II. The core aspect of this version is YOLO9000, jointly trained on the COCO test-dev and the much bigger ImageNet classification dataset [15]. A hierarchical WordTree structure is harnessed enabling

YOLO9000 to detect more than 9000 object classes while retaining fast inference. Despite these enhancements, YOLOv2 also has difficulty in detection of small objects and exact localization. However, the accuracy gap with two stage detectors is significantly narrowed, proving that real-time, large scale object detection is possible [13].

TABLE II: Performance of YOLOv2

Model	Dataset	mAP	FPS
YOLO V2	PASCAL VOC 2007	78.60%	67
YOLO V2	COCO	21.60%	40-90

Advantages:

- (i) Anchor boxes and batch normalization improved accuracy
- (ii) Capable of detecting over 9000 classes

Limitations:

- (i) Struggled with very small objects
- (ii) Feature extraction capability is limited compared to later models

F. YOLOv3(2018) (Multi-Scale Detection and Deeper Networks)

Released in 2018 [10], YOLOv3 marked a significant technical advancement in precision and resilience compared to its earlier versions. The network framework is upgraded to Darknet-53, where 53 convolutional layers, with residual skip connections comparable to ResNet, are used. Improvement in gradient flow are seen, powerful feature extraction is made feasible, due to its intensified architecture, additionally popular classification networks like ResNet-101 on ImageNet are outperformed by YOLOv3 all while staying efficient [28]. The Image-10 shows the architectural design of the YOLOv3.

Fig. 9: Architecture of YOLOv2

A pivotal breakthrough in YOLOv3 is multi-scale detection. The model produced predictions at three separate scales: 13x13, 25x26, and 52x52 rather than predicting objects from a single feature map. Each scale is attributed to detect objects of varied sizes, substantially enhancing performance on small and medium objects, hence overcoming the limitations faced in YOLOv1 and YOLOv2. Usage of anchor boxes, refined from k-means clustering, is done in the detection layers, and every single scale specialized in managing a particular set of anchor shapes [10].

With regard to classification, YOLOv3 shifted from the softmax function to independent logistic classifiers (sigmoid outputs) for each class, enabling the model to manage multi-label predictions, where multiple categories could be assigned to one object. Strong outputs are attained by YOLOv3 on the COCO dataset [14], reaching AP50 of 57.9, bringing it into competition with Faster R-CNN and RetinaNet concurrently being notably faster, running at 20-45 FPS depending on the size of the model which is shown in Table-III. Even though the average precision (AP) at stricter IoU threshold (AP75) is lesser than Two-stage methods, it facilitated the best trade-off between accuracy and speed at the time [10].

TABLE III: Performance of YOLOv3

Model	Dataset	AP@50	FPS
YOLO V3	COCO	57.90%	20-45

Advantages:

- (i) Multi-scale detection for objects of various sizes
- (ii) Uses a strong feature extractor backbone, i.e., Darknet-53

Limitations:

- (i) The model is larger, making it slower on low-end hardware
- (ii) No refinement post-processing

G. YOLOv4 (2020) (Optimized for accuracy and speed)

Introduced by Bochkovskiy et al, in 2020, YOLO4 concentrated on improvising in the practical field and optimized the engineering concepts instead of coming out with a totally new conceptual architecture [16]. Achieving the state-of-the-art accuracy while balancing real time inference is its aim, which made it suitable for both research and industrial use. Many key innovations in framework, training and post-processing are introduced by YOLOv4. Its backbone network is upgraded to CSPDarknet53(Cross-Stage Partial Darknet), reducing computation and usage of memory while advancing smooth progression. The Image-11 shows the architectural design of the YOLOv4.

In CSPDarknet53, feature maps are divided into two parts and later merges them together, making it more efficient for learning without increasing parameters [15]. A Spatial Pyramid Pooling (SPP) block is paired with this backbone., to collect multi-scale spatial information, and a Path Aggregation Network (PANet) neck is also paired to enhance feature fusion across scales. Improvement in simultaneous detection of small, medium and large objects is made by these architectural components [29].

A series of training improvements, jointly called a “bag of freebies” or a “bag of specials”, are introduced by YOLOv4, which included:

- (i) Self-adversarial training (SAT) strongly perturbs images during training.
- (ii) CIoU loss to handle bounding box regression more effectively.

- (iii) Mosaic data augmentation, where four images are combined into one to enhance small-object detection.
- (iv) Mish activation function, improving feature representation.
- (v) DropBlock regularization, enhancing generalization.

These techniques combined together, enabled YOLOv4 to attain a mAP of 43.5% on the COCO dataset while functioning at 65 FPS on a Tesla V100 GPU, surpassing YOLOv3 in both speed and accuracy which is shown in Table-IV.

TABLE IV: Performance of YOLOv4

Model	Dataset	mAP	FPS
YOLO V4	COCO	43.50%	65

The strengths of YOLOv4 lay in its balance between precision and speed, modularity, and practical engineering advancements, enabling it to be highly suitable for deployment in real time applications including surveillance, autonomous driving and industrial robotics. Architectural improvements combined with carefully chosen training techniques demonstrated that state-of-the-art results could be yielded without any overly complex model, making YOLOv4 a huge success [16].

In spite of these enhancements, anchor boxes and multi scale predictions are still relied upon by YOLOv4, making provision for further optimizations and anchor free designs, which are later explored in the following versions of YOLO. However, a huge milestone is reached

in real time, high accuracy object detection, by YOLOv4, bridging the gap between practical deployment and academic research.

Advantages:

- (i) Speed-accuracy trade-off improved using CSP-Darknet53
- (ii) Advanced techniques such as mosaic data augmentation and Mish activation are introduced

Limitations:

- (i) Harder to train from scratch due to complex architecture
- (ii) Optimal results require powerful and high-performance GPUs

Fig. 11: Architecture of YOLOv4

H. YOLOv5(2020) (Accessible, Modular and production ready)

Ultralytics released YOLOv5 in 2020 and marking a notable shift from prior YOLO versions by focusing profoundly on modularity, usability, and deployment [17].

Fig. 10: Architecture of YOLOv3

In contrast to earlier YOLO models, which are mainly implemented in Darknet, PyTorch. YOLOv5 makes it more accessible to developers, researchers, and integrating support for training, evaluation, and deployment pipelines. The Image-12 shows the architectural design of the YOLOv5.

The single stage detection philosophy is retained in the architecture of YOLOv5 along with the anchor-based predictions from the previous YOLO versions. The model comes in various pre-defined sizes — nano (YOLOv5n), small (YOLOv5s), medium (YOLOv5m), large (YOLOv5l), and extra-large (YOLOv5x). Every versions of YOLOv5 allow users to select the desired trade-off between speed and precision depending on hardware constraints. Similar to YOLOv4, the backbone of YOLOv5 uses a CSP (cross stage partial) approach in combination with PANet- style feature aggregation for the neck and decoupled head for classification and bounding box regression [17].

Various engineering advancements are introduced to make training and deployment easy. Robustness is improved by built-in data augmentation strategies. The strategies like mosaic, mixup, and HSV colour jitter. Memory usage decreased with automatic mixed precision training (AMP) and learning sped up, meanwhile pretrained weights are allowed transfer learning on new datasets. The model supports multi format export, which include TorchScript, ONNX, CoreML, and TensorRT. This make the model extensively deployable across cloud, mobile, and embedded systems [30].

YOLOv5 achieved performance results relative to YOLOv4, with reported mAPs of 50%-55% on COCO datasets relying on model size [17], it also offered faster inference (up to 140 FPS for smaller variants) which is shown in Table-V. Optimized label assignment strategies combined with its anchor-based estimations, allowed precise detection across objects of all sizes.

TABLE V: Performance of YOLOv5

Model	Dataset	mAP	FPS
YOLO v5	COCO	50%–55%	140

The primary significant advancement of YOLOv5 lay in its practicality instead of conceptual novelty. YOLOv5 accelerated the adoption of YOLO in research and industry by providing a completely integrated, modular, and deployable system. Due to the ease of use, scalability and production ready pipelines, YOLOv5 became the prevailing starting point for real-world object detection projects, from surveillance and robotics to mobile applications.

Regardless of arguments about the lack of formal peer-reviews publication and its naming, YOLOv5 proved that modularity, usability, and engineering advancements

can be as consequential as algorithmic innovations in advancing real world object detection.

Advantages:

- (i) Easy to use, lightweight, and offers rapid training and inference
- (ii) Highly scalable

Limitations:

- (i) Not officially released by Darknet
- (ii) Lower precision compared to newer models

Fig. 12: Architecture of YOLOv5

I. YOLOv6 (2022) (Industrial Grade Efficiency and deployment)

YOLOv6 is released by Meituan in 2022 with a design that concentrated on the industrial deployment [18]. In contrast to YOLOv5 which is more research and community driven, practical, large-scale applications are targeted by YOLOv6 including autonomous driving, retail analytics, and robotics, where efficiency, speed and deployment on resource-constrained devices are critical.

A new EfficientRep Backbone and a Rep-PAN Neck is introduced by the architecture of YOLOv6 [30]. These components are adapted from re-parameterized techniques, where complicated multi-branch structures used during training are rationalized into lightweight single-path structures at the time of inference. Inference speed is drastically improved without forfeiting accuracy, due to this re-parameterization, making YOLOv6 one of the most efficient detectors available [18].

YOLOv6 adopted a decoupled head design for the detection head, which separated classification and regression branches, allowing the model to refine feature learning distinctively for object localization and category prediction, improving overall precision. Advanced label assignment strategies are incorporated including SimOTA (from YOLOX). SimOTA dynamically matching predictions to ground-truth labels based on IoU and confidence, ensuring better training stability [18].

On the basis of training optimizations, YOLOv6 integrated distillation-based techniques, where smaller

Fig. 13: Architecture of YOLOv6

models learned and adapted from larger ones to attain efficiency. Improved loss functions are also integrated into the model, enhancing bounding box regression by considering angle and distance factors leading to more accurate localisation compared to earlier CIoU or GIoU losses. The Image-13 shows the architectural design of the YOLOv6.

Impressive results are achieved by YOLOv6 which is shown in Table-VI. Higher mAP scores compared to YOLOv5 are achieved on the COCO dataset, all while maintaining faster inference speeds. The primary contribution of YOLOv6 lay in its deployment-oriented design philosophy. The gap between cutting-edge research and real-world usability, which offered models optimized by GPUs, AI accelerators and edge devices [18]. The combination of decoupled head, re-parameterization and enhanced label assignment strengthened YOLOv6 as the industrial- level object detector, widely used in real-time applications.

TABLE VI: Performance of YOLOv6

Model	Dataset	mAP	FPS
YOLO V6	COCO	43.50%	459

Advantages:

- (i) Industrial-grade optimization (Meituan)
- (ii) Improved training efficiency with quantization support

Limitations:

- (i) Inference is slightly slower than YOLOv7 on the same hardware
- (ii) Initially offered less open-source flexibility

J. YOLOv7 (2022) (Trainable Optimizations and Efficient Layer Aggregation)

Representing a significant evolution in the YOLO series, YOLOv7 is released in 2022, it combined the architectural innovations with trainable optimization techniques. In contrast to the former versions of YOLO whose main focus is on backbone and engineering advancements, Efficient Layer Aggregation Networks (ELAN) is introduced by YOLOv7, simultaneously enhanced training strategies are introduced improving speed and accuracy. This rendered it suitable for re-search and production environments which required high-performance real-time detection [19]. YOLOv7 leverages ELAN modules in its backbone architecture, which proficiently unified features across multiple layers while retaining gradient flow. Deeper networks are allowed to be trained without the risk of disappearing gradients or redundancy in feature maps, due to this unique design. A modified PANet structure for multi-scale feature fusion is employed by the neck, allowing detection of small, medium, and large objects simultaneously. Replication-based re-parameterization techniques are also used by YOLOv7, enabling simplification of more complex training structures at inference time for faster deployment. The Image-14 shows the architectural design of the YOLOv7.

A series of trainable “bag of freebies” advancements are incorporated in YOLOv7, which are fixed in earlier versions. These contained dynamic label assignment, adaptive loss scaling, and learnable augmentation strategies, optimizing gradient flow training, increasing stability, and improving convergence. Classification and regression branches are separated due to decoupling of detection heads, enabling specialized optimization

for each task. Although anchor-based predictions are preserved, but dynamic assignment decreased the dependency on manually tuned anchors, enhancing accuracy on diverse datasets [19].

In Table-VII it is shown that YOLOv7 achieved state-of-the-art performance among real time detectors, outperforming YOLOv4 and YOLOv5 in speed as well as mAP, on benchmark datasets like COCO. Noticeable improvements are seen in small-object detection due to advanced multi-scale feature aggregation.

TABLE VII: Performance of YOLOv7

Model	Dataset	mAP	FPS
YOLOv7	COCO	56.80%	160

Significance of YOLOv7 lies in its amalgamation of architecture and trainable optimizations. The model achieved higher precision without sacrificing inference speed by making previously fixed components learnable, which paved the way for later anchor-free designs like YOLOX and YOLOv8. Its modular, competent design coupled with real-time performance, deployed YOLOv7 as a practical choice for both research and industrial applications.

Advantages:

- (i) State-of-the-art accuracy and speed on COCO
- (ii) Efficient model scaling and E-ELAN architecture

Limitations:

- (i) Resource-intensive training
- (ii) Built-in segmentation or tracking features were still lacking

Fig. 14: Architecture of YOLOv7

K. YOLOv8 (2023) (Anchor-free, user centric and flexible)

Released by Ultralytics in January 2023, YOLOv8 culminated a significant redesign of the YOLO family, focusing on flexible, simple and anchor-free detection

[20]. YOLOv8 adopted an anchor-free approach unlike the previous versions of YOLO, which relied on anchor boxes for bounding box predictions. Each detection head in this anchor free approach directly predicts object centers, widths, and heights. The need for carefully tuned anchor configurations is diminished, simplifying training, and improving adaptability across different datasets.

A revised backbone and neck structure is introduced in the architecture of YOLOv8. Yolov8 is building upon ideas from PANet and CSPNet with the idea of refining for lightweight estimation. The decoupling of detection head separated regression and classification tasks, improving specialization. The focus on direct box prediction and elimination of anchors was improved by YOLOv8, along with improvement in in speed and generalization, particularly for datasets with diverse object sizes and aspect ratios [21]. The Image-15 shows the architectural design of the YOLOv8.

The intuitive and accessible framework makes YOLOv8 stand out. Entirely built in PyTorch, APIs were offered to simplify training, evaluation, and deployment of models. Models can be customized quickly by the users and then exported into ONNX, TensiroRT, or OpenVINO, allowing smooth operation across, clouds platforms, mobile and edge devices and hardware. Developers were allowed to choose the right balance between speed and accuracy according to their needs, due to the availability of multiple model sizes [21].

Impressive results were demonstrated by YOLOv8 in terms of performance which is shown in Table-VIII. The largest variant, YOLOv8x achieved 53.9% mAP@0.5 on the COCO dataset. It surpassed its previous versions, while maintaining fast and efficient processing. The YOLOv8n ran at over 300FPS, which made it ideal for real-time tasks. Yolov8 is a multi- task framework, since it extended support for segmentation and classification apart from detection. The simplicity and deployment-focused design further strengthened the dominance of YOLO in real world computer vision.

TABLE VIII: Performance of YOLOv8

Model	Dataset	mAP	FPS
YOLOv8	COCO	53.90%	300

Advantages:

- (i) Has a modular design that supported detection, segmentation, and classification
- (ii) Improvised architecture and simple deployment via Ultralytics

Limitations:

- (i) Computation is slightly heavier than YOLOv5
- (ii) Instability faced with custom datasets initially

Fig. 15: Architecture of YOLOv8

L. YOLOv9 (2024) (Gradient-optimized and fine-grained detection)

Released in 2024, YOLOv9 concentrated on enhanced gradient optimization and feature aggregation to improve detection accuracy, for complicated multi-object and multi-task cases [22]. YOLOv9 implemented Programmable Gradient Information (PGI) to amplify gradient flow across layers and tasks, nothing like its previous versions that primarily focused on deployment and architecture. Enhancement in gradient flow, enabled the ability of the network to absorb fine-grained features more effectively, optimizing convergence and overall precision.

CSP and Efficient Layer Aggregation Network (ELAN) modules are combined with attention mechanisms for the backbone to sustain detailed spatial information. A multi-scale feature fusion strategy is adopted by the neck to enhance the ability of the network to detect small and overlapping objects. There is decoupling of the detection head, which helped maintaining segregated branches for classification and regression, while also integrating trainable label assignment strategies for better training stability. The Image-16 shows the architectural design of the YOLOv9.

The anchor-free approach is inherited from the previ-

ous version by simplifying the prediction of bounding boxes. Without slowing down inference speed, YOLOv9 had improved accuracy on complex datasets. The combination of multi-task learning with optimized gradient flow made it possible, along with an architecture that supported dynamic scaling. Choice can be made by users among lightweight models for embedded devices or larger variants for higher precision applications [22].

Benchmarks highlight YOLOv9's strong performance. 55.2% mAP@0.5 was achieved by the YOLOv9 model on the COCO dataset which is shown in Table IX. It surpassed YOLOv8 while sustaining real-time speeds of approximately 60-100 FPS, according to the variants. The fine-grained detection makes it particularly effective for small objects, dense scenes, or overlapping classes, ensuring precise detection even in challenging conditions.

TABLE IX: Performance of YOLOv9

Model	Dataset	mAP	FPS
YOLOv9	COCO	55.20%	60 – 100

The major significance of YOLOv9 lies in its fusion of gradient programming, architecture, and multi-task optimization. YOLOv9 set a new standard for high accuracy and real-time detection. YOLOv9 prioritizes gradient

Fig. 16: Architecture of YOLOv9

efficiency and fine-grained feature learning. Subsequent YOLO models are influenced by this version, demonstrating that internal optimization strategies, more than simply demonstrating architectural depth or width, can substantially advance detection performance all while maintaining deployability [22].

Advantages:

- (i) Introduction of Programmable Gradient Information (PGI) and GELAN backbone
- (ii) Higher precision and robustness on complex datasets

Limitations:

- (i) Huge model size, not suitable for real-time on edge devices
- (ii) Training setup is more complex

M. YOLOv10 (2024) (Transformer Integration and contextual awareness)

Released in mid-2024, YOLOv10 depicted a significant evolution of the YOLO series by incorporating

transformer-based modules into the traditional convolutional backbone [23]. Improving contextual reasoning and long-range feature interactions, particularly essential for the detection of small or occluded objects in complex scenes, is the key motivation of YOLOv10. In contrast to purely CNN-based YOLO models, YOLOv10 amalgamated the efficiency of convolutional layers with the attention mechanisms of transformers to record both local and global information.

A CSP-like convolutional structure is retained by the backbone of YOLOv10, but transformer blocks are incorporated at the intermediate stages. These blocks enabled the network to simulate relationships across the whole image, refining detection performance in cluttered or dark environments. A multi-scale feature aggregation approach is used by the neck which combined ideas from the PANet and ELAN, while the decoupled detection head is constant, maintaining different branches for the classification and bounding box regression [23]. The Image-17 shows the architectural design of the YOLOv10.

The anchor-free approach is retained by YOLOv10, further rationalizing predictions and minimizing dependence on dataset-specific anchor tuning. Improvement in convergence and stability at the time of training is done by optimizing label assignment and loss function for transformer-enhanced features. Adaptation of various hardware constraints and deployment scenarios in the model are ensured by multi-scale training and dynamic input resizing. Improvements of YOLOv10 over the preceding versions are demonstrated by performance benchmarks. YOLOv10 attained 56.5% mAP@0.5, on the COCO dataset, outperforming YOLOv9, particularly on small and occluded objects. Feasibility of real-time inference remained, with speeds of 50-90 FPS on latest GPUs, relying on the model variant which is shown in Table-X.

TABLE X: Performance of YOLOv10

Model	Dataset	mAP	FPS
YOLOv10	COCO	56.50%	50 – 90

The fusion of convolutional efficiency with transformer-based contextual reasoning made YOLOv10 very significant comparative to the previous versions, which enabled YOLO to manage more complex visual scenes while preserving real-time performance. The combination of global feature awareness with modular, scalable design in YOLOv10 sets the stage for upcoming YOLO versions. These future versions can incorporate even more enhanced attention mechanisms and multi-task capabilities without sacrificing deploy ability or speed [23].

Advantages:

- (i) Faster inference
- (ii) Latency, accuracy and efficiency are outstandingly balanced

Limitations:

- (i) Limited support across platforms
- (ii) Specialized domains have fewer testings

N. YOLOv11 (2025) – (Efficiency, Robustness, and Next-generation Real-time detection)

The latest advancement in the YOLO series is the YOLOv11 which is released by Ultralytics. The legacy of real-time object detection is continued all while expanding its capabilities to multiple computer vision tasks such as object detection, instance segmentation, classification of image, pose estimation and oriented bounding box detection, the model is suitable for a wide range of applications – from research to industrial use and edge deployment, due to its emphasis on precision and efficiency [24].

The architecture of YOLOv11 is incorporated with a hybrid backbone. It balances convolutional layers with

Fig. 17: Architecture of YOLOv10

lightweight transformer modules. Advanced components such as C3k2 (Convolutional block with parallel Spatial Attention), SPPF (Spatial Pyramid Pooling Fast), and C2PSA (Convolutional block with Parallel Spatial Attention) are introduced in the architecture of YOLOv11. Finer spatial features can be extracted by the network with the help of these innovations, particularly enhancing detection of small and overlapping objects [24].

The head and neck have faced modern optimizations, advancements in multi-scale feature fusion and an improvised decoupled head, has been made. Several variants are offered by YOLOv11, in sizes (n, s, m, l, and x) – each variant designed for a different balance between speed and accuracy. Mobile and edge devices may have the smaller variants like YOLOv11n (nano) optimized for them, while the larger versions like YOLOv11x deliver state-of-the-art accuracy for high-end systems. Unlike earlier versions, YOLOv11 can attain better accuracy with fewer parameters. YOLOv11x achieves approximately 54.7% mAP, illustrating substantial improvements in accuracy and recall matrix. The Image-18 shows the architectural design of the YOLOv11.

The model supports multiple export formats such as ONNX, TensorRT, CoreML, and OpenVINO, making it highly deployment-friendly. Multi-task learning is also supported by the model, allowing to perform several types of vision tasks within one framework by a single model, decreasing computational redundancy.

The strengths of YOLOv11 lie in its balance between speed, accuracy, and versatility, which makes it ideal for real-time vision systems. YOLOv11’s advancements over YOLOv10 are incremental rather than revolutionary, making it one of the most efficient and powerful real-time object detection frameworks today [24]. In Table-XI a performance score for YOLOv11 is shown.

TABLE XI: Performance of YOLOv11

Model	Dataset	mAP	FPS
YOLOv11	COCO	54.70%	60 – 100

The combination of accuracy, efficiency, and adaptability contributes to the importance and relevance of YOLOv11. It is developed and designed not only for academic research but also for large-scale industry adoption. It makes YOLOv11 one of the most versatile real-time object detection systems till date. YOLOv11 has set a benchmark for the upcoming next-generation computer vision system by culminating the YOLO innovations of over a decade into one [24].

Advantages:

- (i) Efficiency and accuracy improved due to enhanced feature extraction
- (ii) Improved small-object detection and lightweight deployment options

Limitations:

- (i) Limited benchmarks and adoption
- (ii) Fine-tuning for compatibility with earlier pipelines may be required.

Fig. 18: Architecture of YOLOv11

IV. APPLICATIONS OF YOLO

YOLO has found applications in a strikingly broad spectrum due to its proficiency in performing real-time object detection with high precision. It is employed for monitoring public spaces, detecting unauthorized entrant in restricted areas, and detecting potentially dangerous objects such as weapons or unattended luggage. This makes it almost a staple in the domain of security and surveillance. These competencies have made it vital in

ensuring public safety and obstructing threats in airports, railway stations and other sensitive locations. YOLO is utilized in autonomous vehicles to identify pedestrians, traffic lights, vehicles, and road signs which makes it a major beneficiary in the automotive industry. Rapid feedback makes YOLO models possible for self-driving cars to make decisions instantly, guaranteeing both safety and effectiveness when navigating [25].

YOLO based systems have been integrated largely in the healthcare sector, in several ways, such as medical scans detecting tumors, analysing anomalies in X-rays or CT images, and also supervising activities of patients such as accidental falls. YOLO is widely used during the pandemic for monitoring compliance with protective measures, including face mask detection in public places and hospitals. Smart checkout systems in the retail stores also use YOLO by automatically detecting items without barcode, while also being employed to monitor shelves for misplaced or missing products, hence optimizing inventory management. YOLO has been leveraged in the agricultural domain as well, it helps identify crop diseases, detect pests, and also track livestock behaviour, reducing losses and improving yields through timely interventions which help farmers a great deal [25].

YOLO serves as the “eyes” of machines, in the robotics and industrial automation, allowing robots to detect, pick, and sort objects on assembly lines or assembly drones in inspection and navigation tasks. YOLO has also been adopted by sports analytics to track movements of players, analyze ball trajectories, and calculate team strategies in real-time. It enriches both coaching and broadcasting. YOLO has its applications beyond human-centered domains, such that in the environmental monitoring, assisting researchers in tracking wildlife populations, detecting poaching activities, and studying ecosystems. With the growth of immersive technologies, augmented and virtual reality is also supported by YOLO by allowing real-time object interaction and spatial awareness, which creates more dynamic user experiences. YOLO is vastly used in the field of military and defense, drones and battlefield monitoring systems. YOLO is used to detect movements of enemies, their vehicles, weapons, offering strategic perks in mission planning and threat detection [25].

The versatility of YOLO lies in its speed and accuracy, making it feasible for everyday applications such as retail and healthcare solutions and highly specialized domains such as defense and environmental monitoring. The adaptability feature of YOLO is to diverse environments accentuates its promise of success as a cornerstone technology in the era of intelligent [25].

TABLE XII: Comparison Between YOLO and Traditional Object Detection Frameworks (R-CNN Family and SSD) [26]

Aspect	Traditional Detectors (R-CNN, Fast R-CNN, Faster R-CNN)	SSD (Single Shot MultiBox Detector)	YOLO (You Only Look Once)
Detection Approach	Two-stage detection: (1) Region proposal generation, (2) Classification of each proposed region.	Single-stage detector using multiple feature maps for multi-scale object detection.	Single-stage detector that treats detection as a <i>single regression problem</i> , predicting bounding boxes and class probabilities in one pass.
Region Proposal Method	External methods (Selective Search or RPN) are required for generating candidate regions.	No separate proposal stage; detections are made directly from feature maps.	No region proposal stage; predictions are generated directly from the entire image grid.
Architecture Complexity	Multi-stage and computationally heavy pipeline; complex training and fine-tuning.	Moderately complex; integrates detection into a single network but uses multiple feature layers.	Simple, unified CNN architecture that is easy to train end-to-end.
Speed (FPS)	Relatively slow due to sequential proposal and classification stages.	Faster than R-CNN but slower than YOLO in high-resolution video tasks.	Extremely fast real-time detection (>30-60 FPS), suitable for low-latency applications.
Accuracy on Small Objects	High precision but depends on region proposals; robust for small and overlapping objects.	Performs well on medium and large objects but struggles with very small ones.	Early versions traded accuracy for speed, but recent versions (YOLOv8-v11) significantly improved small-object detection.
Computation Cost	High due to multiple forward passes and RPN computation.	Moderate; depends on feature-map scales used.	Low; single forward pass for the entire image reduces computation.
Deployment and Training	Difficult; requires multiple training phases and post-processing.	Easier than R-CNN but still complex due to multi-scale anchors.	Straightforward end-to-end training and deployment on various hardware platforms.
Primary Focus	Maximizing detection accuracy and localization precision.	Balancing speed and accuracy for diverse object scales.	Achieving real-time inference while maintaining high accuracy and simple design.
Best-Suited Applications	Offline or high-accuracy applications like image annotation or medical imaging.	General-purpose detection where moderate speed and accuracy are acceptable.	Real-time scenarios such as autonomous driving, video surveillance, and robotics.

V. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF YOLO AND OTHER OBJECT DETECTION MODELS

A breakthrough shift in object detection is brought by YOLO by segmenting object detection as a single regression issue instead of a multi-stage process. Two-step approach is used in the traditional detectors such as R-CNN and its variants. First, region proposals are

generated. Then, classification of each proposed region takes place. Unlike these, an entire image is processed in one forward pass of a convolutional neural network by YOLO, which forecast bounding boxes as well as class probabilities simultaneously. The difference in the architecture enables YOLO to attain real-time detection speeds, making it highly compatible with applications

TABLE XIII: YOLO Versions: Architecture, Input Size, and Feature Maps

YOLO Version	Year	Backbone	Default Input Size	Feature Maps / Heads
YOLOv1	2016	GoogLeNet-like	448×448	7×7 (s32)
YOLOv2	2017	Darknet-19	416×416	13×13 + passthrough
YOLOv3	2018	Darknet-53	320/416/608	3 heads (52,26,13)
YOLOv4	2020	CSPDarknet-53	608×608	3 heads
YOLOv5	2020	CSP (v5s-x)	640×640	3 heads (80,40,20)
YOLOv6	2022	EfficientRep	640×640	3 heads
YOLOv7	2022	E-ELAN	640×640	3 heads (P3-P5)
YOLOv8	2023	C2f + PAN-FPN	640×640	3 heads
YOLOv9	2024	GELAN + PGI	640×640	3 heads
YOLOv10	2024	NMS-free design	640×640	3 heads
YOLOv11	2024	Ultralytics C3/C2*	640×640	3 heads

TABLE XIV: YOLO Versions: Output Tensor Structure and Representative Performance

YOLO Version	Output Tensor per Head	Performance (COCO/VOC)
YOLOv1	$7 \times 7 \times 30$	VOC07 mAP 63.4% @ 45 FPS
YOLOv2	$A \times (5+C)$, $A=5$	+5% over YOLOv1
YOLOv3	$3 \times (5+C) = 255$ ch	COCO AP 33.0
YOLOv4	$3 \times (5+C)$	AP 43.5, 65 FPS
YOLOv5	$3 \times (5+C)$	Strong real-time AP
YOLOv6	$3 \times (5+C)$	35.9 AP @ 1234 FPS
YOLOv7	$3 \times (5+C)$	Up to 56.8 AP
YOLOv8	$3 \times (5+C)$	SOTA real-time
YOLOv9	$3 \times (5+C)$	Competitive AP
YOLOv10	$3 \times (5+C)$	Better latency/AP
YOLOv11	$3 \times (5+C)$	Higher speed and accuracy

which required low latency, like autonomous driving or video surveillance [26].

Due to the dependent on external region proposal methods and multiple stages of feature extraction, traditional detectors like R-CNN and Fast R-CNN are significantly slower even though there is no compromise in accuracy. This drawback is improvised by the Faster R-CNN which introduced a Region Proposal Network (RPN) integrating proposal generation within the network itself which did increase its speed but still could not match the frame-per-second (FPS) performance of YOLO. Similar to YOLO, single shot detection is also performed by SSD, but it uses multi-scale feature maps for detecting objects of various sizes. A good outcome is obtained by SSD on medium and large objects but YOLO has evolved to improve the detection of small objects while retaining superior speed.

A key trade-off between traditional detectors and YOLO is speed vs accuracy. Detection of small or overlapping objects traded some precision for speed in the earlier versions of YOLO. Nevertheless, this gap has been narrowed by recent YOLO iterations. They have attained competitive accuracy with Faster R-CNN while retaining their hallmark efficiency [26]. The simplicity in deployment is also a distinct differentiating factor and the single-network architecture of YOLO is easier to train end-to-end in relation to R-CNN variant which require more complex pipelines. The Table-XII shows the Comparison of YOLO with respect to Traditional Object Detection Frameworks.

YOLO is refined for scenarios where real-time perfor-

mance and end-to-end simplicity is vital. On the other hand, maximum detection accuracy is focused on, by R-CNN-based models, at the expense of higher computational requirements. A middle ground is occupied by SSD, offering single-pass detection with moderate speed and accuracy. The optimal model varies according to the application's priorities and it emphasizes speed, accuracy, or computational cost [26].

VI. MERITS AND LIMITATIONS OF YOLO

YOLO is capable of identifying small, medium, and large objects in real-time, making it stand out as a fast and versatile object detection framework. Its all-in-one design enables handling of detection, classification, segmentation, and even pose by a single model. This reduces deployment overhead and simplifies workflows for developers. Global context information is leveraged by the model, allowing it to maintain high accuracy across complex scenes. Moreover, a wide range of platforms are supported by YOLO, from GPUs and CPUs to edge devices and cloud servers, making it easy to adapt for time-sensitive applications. The framework's developer friendly tools and APIs further refine training, evaluation, and deployment making it accessible even for non-experts [2].

Nevertheless, YOLO also faces some challenges. The computational demands are huge, particularly for larger models, for efficient training and inference required by powerful hardware. While excellent at general detection, tiny, densely-packed, or overlapping objects challenge YOLO and might produce less precise bounding

boxes compared to two-stage models like Mask R-CNN. Careful tuning and experience to avoid pitfalls such as overfitting datasets, are demanded by its complex architecture, which often necessitates data augmentation and transfer learning. Finally, with the growth in model size, resource consumption and memory requirements can limit deployment in lightweight or mobile scenarios. The Table-?? shows the comparison of YOLO Versions in Terms of Architecture, Input, Feature Maps, Output Tensor, and Performance.

VII. CONCLUSION

YOLO was made faster, simpler, and more efficient than earlier methods due to the revolutionization of real-time object detection done by YOLO. Progressive refinements over the years, from YOLOv1 to YOLOv11, have made it one of the most robust and widely adopted detection systems in the field of computer vision. Single-step detection has enabled YOLO to be utilized in several fields. These include surveillance systems, self-driving vehicles, and robotics.

YOLO appears to have a highly promising future. The main dedication of the field experts is levied on development of lighter and more efficient versions. It can run on mobile and edge devices with constrained computational capacity. An additional key approach, to further enhance accuracy especially for small and overlapping objects, is combination of YOLO with transformer-based architectures and neural attention mechanisms. Integration of IoT in YOLO and video analytics at real-time is anticipated to show an upward trend, allowing intelligent applications in smart cities, agriculture, and industrial automation.

A strong foundation has been set by YOLO for modern object detection research. Newer innovations in deep learning and computer vision are inspired by YOLO's balance of speed, accuracy, and simplicity. With the advancements in technology, YOLO is expected to persist as a key part of future AI systems, pushing the boundaries of what real-time detection can achieve.

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